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1st Project Video

Electrochemical
oxidation of cyclic
and biogenic
substrates for high
efficiency production
of organic chemicals

ELOXYCHEM

eloxychem-horizon.eu
HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-01
1st January 2024 - 30th June 2028

Document control sheet

Project	ELOXYCHEM - Electrochemical oxidation of cyclic and biogenic substrates for high efficiency production of organic chemicals
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Work package leader	Edoardo Nencetti
Dissemination level	Public
Lead Beneficiary	ETA
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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the first project video of the ELOXYCHEM project. The approximately 1:30-minute-long video features recordings from the Kick-Off Meeting held on February 8-9, brief interviews with project partners, and footages of the Evonik plant in Marl, Germany. It also includes a scripted narrative explaining the aim of the ELOXYCHEM project and its innovative approach, addressing the chemical industry's reliance on fossil fuels. By developing a novel dicarboxylic acid production route based on electrochemistry and integrating digitalization for pilot plant monitoring, the project targets to overcome current challenges in the sector.

The goal of the video is to provide a concise overview of the projects main objectives and highlight the potential impact of ELOXYCHEM on the chemical industry.

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Publication and distribution

The first project video (Figure 1) of ELOXYCHEM has been uploaded to the project's YouTube channel and will be made public on January 2, 2025. The video will be subsequently shared across social media platforms, including the project's LinkedIn account and official website.

Once public, it will be accessible via the following link on all the mentioned platforms: <https://youtu.be/70Ub37vuKZY>.

Figure 1: Video thumbnail.

ELOXYCHEM

Partners

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